

Europium(III) as luminescence probe for interactions of a sulfate-reducing microorganism with potentially toxic metals

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ARTICLE INFO

Edited by: Dr Fernando Barbosa

Keywords:

Europium(III) luminescence
Sulfate-reducing bacteria
Europium(III) bioprecipitation
Opalinus clay pore water

ABSTRACT

Microorganisms show a high affinity for trivalent actinides and lanthanides, which play an important role in the safe disposal of high-level radioactive waste as well as in the mining of various rare earth elements. The interaction of the lanthanide Eu(III) with the sulfate-reducing microorganism *Desulfosporosinus hippei* DSM 8344^T, a representative of the genus *Desulfosporosinus* that naturally occurs in clay rock and bentonite, was investigated. Eu(III) is often used as a non-radioactive analogue for the trivalent actinides Pu(III), Am(III), and Cm(III), which contribute to a major part of the radiotoxicity of the nuclear waste. *D. hippei* DSM 8344^T showed a weak interaction with Eu(III), most likely due to a complexation with lactate in artificial Opalinus Clay pore water. Hence, a low removal of the lanthanide from the supernatant was observed. Scanning transmission electron microscopy coupled with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy revealed a bioprecipitation of Eu(III) with phosphates potentially excreted from the cells. This demonstrates that the ongoing interaction mechanisms are more complex than a simple biosorption process. The bioprecipitation was also verified by luminescence spectroscopy, which showed that the formation of the Eu(III) phosphate compounds starts almost immediately after the addition of the cells. Moreover, chemical microscopy provided information on the local distribution of the different Eu(III) species in the formed cell aggregates. These results provide first insights into the interaction mechanisms of Eu(III) with sulfate-reducing bacteria and contribute to a comprehensive safety concept for a high-level radioactive waste repository, as well as to a better understanding of the fate of heavy metals (especially rare earth elements) in the environment.

1. Introduction

The fate of heavy metals in the environment in the presence of microorganisms and the understanding of the underlying processes gain more and more interest in the scientific community. Reasons can be seen in the importance of microorganisms in mining activities of different metals but also in the safety of disposal sites for high-level radioactive waste.

Anthropogenic sources of metal input in the environment can be divided into five main streams: metalliferous mining and smelting, industry, atmospheric deposition, agriculture, and waste disposal (Ross, 1994). The increasing use of Eu(III) as one representative of the rare earth elements (REE) in high-tech products may increase the risk of environmental contaminations due to accidents in waste disposal sites.

Microorganisms which are ubiquitous in nature, for example 10⁸ cells per g soil (Raynaud and Nunan, 2014), are essential for the global biogeochemical cycling of elements (Haferburg and Kothe, 2007). They can adapt to heavy metal-rich environments by biosorption, bioprecipitation, extracellular sequestration, transport mechanisms, and/or chelation (Lloyd and Macaskie, 2002). In more detail, due to the negative charge of the cell envelope, microorganisms can accumulate metals either by metabolism-independent, passive, or metabolism-dependent, active processes (Haferburg and Kothe, 2007). Due to the high density of metal-binding groups: phosphoryl and carboxyl as well as amine/imidazole and thiol, the cell wall highly influences the accumulation of metals by microbes. For example, this could be demonstrated for curium (III) and different cell wall compartments of *Lysinibacillus sphaericus* JG-A 12 (Moll et al., 2020). Hufton et al. considered the bacterial cell

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2023.115474>

Received 4 July 2023; Received in revised form 7 September 2023; Accepted 11 September 2023

Available online 15 September 2023

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wall as the main controlling factor in the biosorption of aqueous uranium(VI) by microorganisms (Hufton et al., 2021). The site density of functional groups of bacterial cell envelopes ranges between 0.1 and 0.9 mmol/g of bacteria within pH 3 and 7 (Cox et al., 1999; Mishra et al., 2010; Moll et al., 2014). The high density of functional groups of bacterial cell envelopes can be seen in comparison with inorganic sorption materials. For instance, basaltic rock exhibits a site density of 0.1 mmol/g for metal binding, whereas for goethite a value of 0.06 mmol/g was determined (Naveau et al., 2005; Tertre et al., 2008). Especially the interaction of REE with microorganisms comprises two sub processes of passive cation attachment to the cell surface and metal uptake with intracellular accumulation (Haferburg and Kothe, 2007). In our previous studies, we could show the particular high affinity of different microorganisms to accumulate Eu(III) and Cm(III) from aqueous solution (e.g., (Moll et al., 2014)). Time-resolved laser-induced fluorescence spectroscopy (TRLFS) was applied as a direct tool to explore the speciation of the trivalent metal ions in these biological systems. Here, we have used the excellent luminescence properties of Eu(III), which makes it possible to use it as a structural probe to extract information on the molecular level (Binnemans, 2015). In agreement with the literature, carboxyl and phosphate moieties were identified as major binding sites for trivalent metal ions on bacterial cell envelopes. Microorganisms are also able to immobilize metals by either complexation with released chelating compounds or precipitation across the cell envelope depending on structural features (Haferburg and Kothe, 2007). As an example, Cm(III) forms strong complexes with pyoverdines secreted by a groundwater strain of *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, as measured by luminescence spectroscopy (Moll et al., 2008). Furthermore, studies with the extreme halophilic archaeon *Halobacterium noricense* DSM 15987^T revealed the formation of two Eu(III) phosphate species using (site-selective) TRLFS (Bader et al., 2019).

In our present study, we have used Eu(III) because it is known as a suitable non-radioactive analog for trivalent actinides (americium and curium) in radioecological studies (Ansoborlo et al., 2006). The aim of this work was to extend the knowledge of microbial Eu(III) interactions to sulfate-reducing bacteria. To the best of our knowledge, there have been no investigations on the interaction of Eu(III) with anaerobic sulfate-reducing microorganisms so far. Therefore, *Desulfosporosinus hippei* DSM 8344^T was used in this study as an important representative of the genus *Desulfosporosinus*, which occurs in various clay formations as well as in bentonite (Bagnoud et al., 2016; Matschiavelli et al., 2019). As members of naturally occurring microbial communities in the potential barrier materials of a final repository for high-level radioactive waste, sulfate-reducing *Desulfosporosinus* spp. can influence the radionuclides released, e.g. in a worst case scenario, in a number of ways as mentioned above. The interactions of this microorganism with U(VI) and its reduction to less-soluble U(IV) were already investigated in detail (Hilpmann et al., 2023). We used artificial Opalinus Clay pore water solution as background electrolyte for the experiments, in order to mimic the natural surroundings of a final repository for nuclear waste in clay rock as closely as possible (Wersin et al., 2011). Furthermore, experiments were performed under anaerobic conditions, which are expected in a nuclear waste disposal after certain time frames (Corkhill and Hyatt, 2018; Standish et al., 2016). In addition to the general interaction behavior, we wanted to prove the possibility of a bio-reduction of Eu(III) to Eu(II) due to the metabolism of the cells in the presence of lactate as an electron donor. Previous studies with another member of the class Clostridia (*Clostridium* sp. 2611) showed the capability of this strain to reduce Eu(III) to Eu(II) under growth and non-growth conditions (Maleke et al., 2019). The bioassociation of Eu(III) on *D. hippei* DSM 8344^T cells was studied on the cellular level by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS), and live-dead staining and on the molecular level by TRLFS. The localization of Eu(III) on the cells was investigated by scanning transmission electron microscopy in combination with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (STEM/EDXS) and by chemical microscopy (Vogel et al., 2021). These

investigations lead to an increased understanding of the interaction behavior of *D. hippei* DSM 8344^T with trivalent lanthanides and actinides.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Cultivation and Eu(III) bioassociation experiment

D. hippei DSM 8344^T was purchased from the Leibniz Institute DSMZ – German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures (DSMZ, Braunschweig, Germany) and cultivated in modified DSM 641 medium (OD₆₀₀ of 0.08 – 0.1 after 42 – 48 h of growth, corresponding to cell numbers of 6×10^5 – 8×10^5 cells/mL) as described elsewhere (Hilpmann et al., 2023).

For Eu(III) bioassociation batch experiments, anoxic Eu(III) solutions with two different concentrations of 60 and 110 μ M at a pH of 5.5 were prepared in sealed serum bottles. Opalinus clay pore solution, whose composition was determined by Wersin et al. (Wersin et al., 2011), served as background electrolyte. Its preparation was described previously (Hilpmann et al., 2023). Furthermore, the solutions contained 10 mM sodium lactate because lactate can serve as an electron donor for a possible reduction of Eu(III) (Maleke et al., 2019). The Eu(III) used for the studies was purchased as EuCl₃ x 6 H₂O (99.9%, Sigma Aldrich) and dissolved in 0.1 M HCl to obtain a stock solution with a concentration of 0.1 M.

Appropriate volumes of the washed cell suspension (in artificial Opalinus Clay pore water) were added to the Eu(III) solution to achieve an optical density in the samples of 0.2 (dry bio mass (DBM) = 0.088 mg/mL, cell numbers: 1.6×10^6 cells/mL).

Suspensions were incubated at room temperature (22 °C). Time-dependent bioassociation studies were performed over periods of up to one week. After the specified exposure times, samples were withdrawn with a syringe, transferred to a tube, and centrifuged at 10,000 x g for 5 min at 18 °C in an anaerobic glove box. The concentration of unbound Eu(III) in the supernatants was determined by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS; ELAN 9000, PerkinElmer, Waltham, MA, USA). For this purpose, cell pellets and liquid phase were separated, 1 mL of the supernatants were taken for the ICP-MS samples and acidified with 10 μ L of concentrated nitric acid. Experiments were performed in triplicate unless otherwise stated.

2.2. Verification of cell viability

For fluorescence microscopy imaging of the Eu(III)-incubated cells, staining was performed using a LIVE/DEAD® BacLight™ Bacterial Viability Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) according to the manufacturer's instructions under anaerobic conditions. Sample preparation and fluorescence microscopy imaging were performed as previously described (Hilpmann et al., 2023).

2.3. Transmission electron microscopy

Eu localization at the single-cell level was performed by transmission electron microscopy (TEM). In particular, bright-field TEM images were recorded with an image-C_s-corrected Titan 80–300 microscope (Field Electron and Ion Company (FEI), Eindhoven, The Netherlands) operated at an accelerating voltage of 300 kV. High-angle annular dark-field scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) imaging and spectrum imaging analysis based on energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDXS) were performed on a Talos F200X microscope (FEI) operated at 200 kV and equipped with a Super-X EDX detector system. Only one incubation time (24 h) and one Eu(III) concentration (110 μ M) was examined, as well as a reference sample without Eu(III) incubation.

TEM specimen preparation was performed as previously described by Völkner et al. (Völkner et al., 2021, 2019). In particular, incubation took place as described above (see 2.2.2). Afterwards, samples were

centrifuged anaerobically (18 °C and 10,000 x g for 5 min) and washed in anoxic 0.1 M sodium cacodylate buffer at pH 7.2. For subsequent cell fixation, the pellet was resuspended in the same buffer containing 2% glutaraldehyde. Further processing of the samples was done aerobically at the Center for Regenerative Therapies Dresden (CRTD) (Völkner et al., 2021, 2019). Semi-thin sections were cut using a Leica UC6 ultra microtome and stained with toluidine blue/borax to identify potential regions of interest, followed by ultrathin sectioning using a diamond knife. Carbon-coated slot grids were used to collect the ultrathin sections.

2.4. Time-resolved laser-induced fluorescence spectroscopy

Time-resolved laser-induced fluorescence spectroscopy (TRLFS) measurements were used to investigate the cell-bound Eu(III) species, as well as Eu(III) species in the supernatants. Both, supernatants and washed and resuspended cells, were analyzed separately at room temperature in a quartz glass cuvette (Hellma Analytics, Mühlheim, Germany). Therefore, cell suspensions were centrifuged anaerobically at 18 °C and 10,000 x g for 5 min 1 mL of each supernatant was transferred directly into the cuvette. Cells were washed and resuspended in artificial Opalinus Clay pore water solution (pH 5.5). Furthermore, a blank solution without cells was prepared, as well.

Eu(III) luminescence experiments were conducted as previously described (e.g., (Moll et al., 2021) and references therein). Experimental details concerning the luminescence measurements and data evaluation are summarized in the [Supplementary Information](#) section. The relative peak intensity ratio, $R_{E/M}$, which provides information about the ligand field of Eu(III) and the coordination environment, was determined by forming the ratio for the integral intensities I of the 7F_2 -to- 7F_1 band using equation S11.

To study the speciation of Eu(III) in the cell pellets during the first four hours of incubation, a slightly different experimental approach was used. In this approach, 2 mL were taken from the serum bottles at each sampling, centrifuged (5 min, 18 °C, 10,000 x g), resuspended in 1 mL Opalinus Clay pore solution (pH 5.5), and transferred to a quartz cuvette. Spectra were recorded at room temperature using a diode-pumped solid-state laser (Ekspla NT230, Vilnius, Lithuania) at an excitation wavelength of 394 nm. The laser pulse width was in the range of 5–10 ns and the pulse repetition rate was 50 Hz. The spectra were detected using an intensified charge-coupled device (ICCD, Andor iStar, DH320T-18 U-63, Lot-Oriel Group, Darmstadt, Germany). A grating of 300 lines/mm was used, and the input signal was amplified by a factor of 4095. To study the lifetimes, a kinetic series was recorded over 21 time points. A total of 200 spectra per time point were averaged. The step size was linearly increased according to the formula $(3 + 3 - x) \mu\text{s}$. The measurements were analyzed using parallel factor analysis (PARAFAC) (Drobot et al., 2015).

2.5. Chemical microscopy

Chemical microscopy is a combination of laser spectroscopy and confocal light microscopy. Measurements were performed with a Raman microscope (LabRAM system, Horiba Jobin Yvon, Lyon, France) using an excitation wavelength of 532 nm. With this analytical method, it is possible to obtain spatially resolved information about the speciation of metals in biological matrices. The general setup was described by M. Vogel et al. (Vogel et al., 2021).

Cell agglomerates after 24 h incubation with 110 μM Eu(III) were examined. Approximately 10 μL of the cell suspension were placed on a microscope slide in an anaerobic box, and the cover slip placed on top was sealed with clear varnish to prevent oxygen from entering during the measurement. The 60x objective was used to produce a laser spot with a diameter of 927 nm. The Eu(III) luminescence was in the wavelength range between 560 and 725 nm (pinhole 200 μm , entrance slit 200 μm , monochromator 300 lines/mm grating). The examined region

of interest (ROI) had a size of 50 \times 50 μm . Each pixel with a size of 1 μm^2 was examined with an exposure time of 10 s. Data acquisition was performed using LabSpec 5 (Horiba Jobin Yvon). Background correction of the spectra was performed using a "rolling ball" algorithm (Sternberg, 1982). The data were deconvoluted using iterative factor analysis (N-way toolbox for Matlab (Andersson and Bro, 2000)) with random initial estimates. To account for physical meanings, the spectra of factors and distributions were restricted to be non-negative (NIFA - non-negative factor analysis) (Vogel et al., 2021).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Eu(III) batch experiments

For the bioassociation experiments with cells of *D. hippei* DSM 8344^T, two different concentrations (60 and 110 μM) were investigated time-dependently. The association kinetics illustrated in Fig. 1 show a slight decrease in the concentrations of Eu(III) in the supernatant and therefore an increase in the amount of cell-associated Eu(III) over time for both initial concentrations. Overall, the amounts of Eu(III) removed from the supernatants were low. In both cases, the process was almost completed after two hours, suggesting a simple biosorption as the main interaction mechanism. Biosorption is defined as the passive binding of a sorptive (metal) to the sorbent (functional groups of the biomass) and is completed within a few hours (Gadd, 2009; Lloyd and Macaskie, 2002). At both concentrations, approximately 14 $\text{mg}_{\text{Eu(III)}/\text{g}_{\text{DBM}}}$ is associated after two hours. This suggests that saturation of the functional groups on the cell surface probably occurred already at the lower concentration. The Eu(III) load corresponds to 8% removed metal for an initial concentration of 110 μM and 16% at 60 μM , respectively. After one week, these values increased only slightly.

For comparison, cells of *Sporomusa* sp. associated more than 90% of the supplied Eu(III), as described in Moll et al. (Moll et al., 2014). Explanations for the low amount of bioassociated Eu(III) by *D. hippei* DSM 8344^T cells could be a lower amount of available functional groups or the groups are somehow blocked for Eu(III) coordination. In addition, a possible strong complexation of Eu(III) in solution could shield the metal ions from interacting with the cells. Another explanation could be the lower initial concentrations of max. 30 μM Eu(III) in the samples of the

Fig. 1. Eu(III) concentrations in the supernatants of the batch experiments with *D. hippei* DSM 8344^T at initial Eu(III) concentrations of 60 and 110 μM (artificial Opalinus Clay pore water, pH 5.5, 10 mM sodium lactate, DBM = 0.088 mg/mL, 1.6×10^6 cells/mL). All data points contain error bars. If not visible, they are covered by the symbols.

experiments with *Sporomusa* sp (Moll et al., 2014).

3.2. Cell viability during Eu(III) exposure

Cell viability was assessed by live/dead staining. Cells not in contact with Eu(III) were alive throughout the whole time of the experiment (168 h). The lower Eu(III) concentration showed almost no effect on the cells (Fig. 2a). Only after one week, some small agglomerates appeared but almost all cells were still alive.

Fluorescence microscopy images of cells incubated with the higher Eu(III) concentration showed a different picture (Fig. 2b). After only two hours, the cells started to aggregate. In addition, some of the cells died during the experiment, as shown by the yellowish and red color of the individual cells and agglomerates. In general, agglomeration is accompanied by an increase in the number of functional groups due to the excretion of various organic compounds. This could explain the slight further association of Eu(III) on cells of *D. hippei* DSM 8344^T after bio-sorption was completed after 2 h of incubation. Hence, the higher Eu(III) concentration is more toxic to the cells. The formation of cell agglomerates under the influence of Eu(III) has already been observed for other microorganisms. For example, the halophilic archaeon *H. noricense* DSM 15987^T showed a strong agglomeration of cells after 48 h at a Eu(III) concentration of 100 μ M (Bader et al., 2019). In this case, a large proportion of the cells also died due to the chemotoxic effect of the lanthanide.

Incubation of the cells of *D. hippei* DSM 8344^T with uranium(VI) also resulted in the formation of cell agglomerates that were significantly larger (Hilpmann et al., 2023). The percentage of dead cells was significantly higher after two hours of incubation with U(VI) than with Eu(III).

3.3. Transmission electron microscopy

The localization of Eu(III) in/on the cells of *D. hippei* DSM 8344^T was investigated by transmission electron microscopy (TEM)-based analyses of ultrathin sections of Eu(III)-incubated cells. In particular, bright-field TEM imaging was combined with spectrum imaging analysis based on energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDXS). Only one Eu(III) concentration (110 μ M) and one incubation time (24 h) was investigated due to the rapid association process and the low amounts of cell-bound Eu(III). Fig. 3 shows the resulting images including the distribution maps of Eu(III), phosphorous and oxygen.

The TEM-based images of the Eu(III)-incubated cells show the formation of locally limited precipitates on the cell surface. These precipitates consist of Eu(III), which is co-localized with phosphorous and oxygen, as determined by EDXS-based element distribution analysis. Both elements showed an increased occurrence in connection with Eu(III). This may indicate a bioprecipitation of Eu(III) with cell-released phosphates. Furthermore, a much smaller proportion of Eu(III) was taken up into the cells, as well. Similar results were seen in the interaction of *Stenotrophomonas bentonitica* with Eu(III), where Eu(III)- and phosphate-containing precipitates were also formed on the cell surface (Ruiz-Fresneda et al., 2020).

3.4. Luminescence spectroscopic studies of the bioassociation process

The interaction processes of *D. hippei* DSM 8344^T with Eu(III) were further elucidated using spectroscopic methods. Fig. 4 shows the recorded spectra (normalized to the ⁷F₁ band) of the supernatants (a, c) and cell pellets (b, d) after different incubation times for the initial Eu(III) concentrations of 60 and 110 μ M. Also shown are the spectra of a 100 μ M Eu(III) solution in 0.1 M hydrochloric acid and blank spectra of Eu(III) in artificial Opalinus clay pore solution in the presence of 10 mM sodium lactate.

Fig. 2. Live/dead staining of the cells of *D. hippei* DSM 8344^T after incubation with a) 60 μ M and b) 110 μ M Eu(III) (artificial Opalinus Clay pore water, pH 5.5, 10 mM sodium lactate) for different incubation times, as well as cell blanks without Eu(III) incubation after 168 h. Cells were stained with LIVE/DEAD® BacLight™ Bacterial Viability Kit; green = living cells, red = dead cells.

110 μM Eu(III)

Fig. 3. Representative bright-field TEM image and corresponding Eu, P, and O element distribution maps of a thin sectioned sample of *D. hippei* DSM 8344^T cells treated with Eu(III) ($[\text{Eu(III)}]_{\text{initial}} = 110 \mu\text{M}$, artificial Opalinus Clay pore water, pH 5.5, 10 mM sodium lactate) for 24 h.

Fig. 4. Eu(III) luminescence spectra measured in the *D. hippei* DSM 8344^T system. a) Supernatants in the presence of 60 μM Eu(III) (artificial Opalinus Clay pore water, pH 5.5, 10 mM sodium lactate). b) Re-suspended cells after contact with 60 μM Eu(III) (artificial Opalinus Clay pore water, pH 5.5). c) Supernatants in the presence of 110 μM Eu(III) (artificial Opalinus Clay pore water, pH 5.5, 10 mM sodium lactate). d) Re-suspended cells after contact with 110 μM Eu(III) (artificial Opalinus Clay pore water, pH 5.5).

For both Eu(III) concentrations, the spectra of the blank samples containing Eu(III) and 10 mM lactate showed no changes compared to those of the supernatants after cell separation. Therefore, the Eu(III) speciation in the supernatants did not change during the experiments. The cells probably did not excrete any metabolites as possible complexing agents for Eu(III), or only in very small amounts. It is also possible that the metabolites produced may have weaker complexing properties than the lactate that is present in excess. Another reason could be the partly low amount of biomass in our experiments. In addition, the cells accumulated relatively small amounts of Eu(III) from the surrounding solution, as shown in Fig. 1.

No influence of the applied Eu(III) concentration on the measured luminescence spectra and lifetimes could be detected. Therefore, all

luminescence spectra of the supernatants were used for the PARAFAC (Drobot et al., 2015) analysis to calculate the spectroscopic Eu(III) speciation in the supernatants. As a result, only one Eu(III) species was present in the solutions after separation of the cells (c.f. Figs S1 and S2). This Eu(III) species described the 1:1 Eu(III) lactate complex as characterized by Barkleit et al. (Barkleit et al., 2014). In all supernatant samples, a mono-exponential luminescence decay with a lifetime of $118 \pm 0.7 \mu\text{s}$ was measured. This is in agreement with the study of Barkleit et al., who also found always a mono-exponential decay with a lifetime of $148 \mu\text{s}$ in the presence of 10 μM Eu(III) and 5 mM lactate at pH 6. Minor deviations can occur because the complexity of the pore water provides the possibility of other non-radiative relaxation of the excited Eu(III), which can lead to a shortening of the lifetime of the lactate

complex. The strong complexation of Eu(III) with lactate found in the supernatants may be another reason for the low levels of cell-associated Eu(III), as it may lead to shielding of Eu(III) from the cellular ligands.

The luminescence spectra of the cells incubated with Eu(III) also showed no differences between the concentrations and time points studied. It is possible that after the initial biosorption of Eu(III) by the cells, no further processes took place, which means that the spectra recorded at the beginning already correspond to those of the later time points. However, there are differences between the spectra of the cells and the blank spectra of Eu(III) with 10 mM sodium lactate in artificial Opalinus Clay pore solution. The cell-bound Eu(III) is characterized by an increased $R_{E/M}$ value of 2.0 compared to 0.8 in the spectrum of the blank solution. As it is clear from the ICP-MS values that the initial binding of Eu(III) to the cells is very rapid, a second experiment was carried out with regular sampling during the incubation period from 0 to 4 h in order to more accurately characterize the speciation at this stage of the experiment. A Eu(III) concentration of 110 μM was investigated. The measured initial spectra (normalized to the ${}^7\text{F}_1$ band) are shown in the SI (Fig. S3). With increasing incubation time, a clear change in the ratio of the ${}^7\text{F}_2$ to the ${}^7\text{F}_1$ band could be observed, indicating complexation of the Eu(III) on the cells. In order to obtain more detailed information on the individual Eu(III) species involved, an evaluation was carried out using PARAFAC (Drobot et al., 2015). The individual spectra of the extracted species and their distribution are shown in Fig. 5. A decay plot for the different species is shown in the supplementary information (Fig. S4).

Using PARAFAC evaluation (Drobot et al., 2015), the single-component spectra of three different Eu(III) species could be obtained (Fig. 5a). Species 1 shows a high agreement with the free Eu^{3+} ion in the Opalinus Clay pore water ($R_{E/M} = 0.52$, lifetime: $113 \pm 5 \mu\text{s}$). It characterizes a Eu(III) species which is only loosely associated with the cells and which is transferred back into solution by resuspension of the cell pellet prior to measurement. Species 2 and 3 are probably cell-associated Eu(III) species with lifetimes of $102 \pm 8 \mu\text{s}$ and $314 \pm 9 \mu\text{s}$, respectively. Due to the relatively short lifetime of species 2, which is below the value of 110 μs for free Eu^{3+} (Barkleit et al., 2014), it can be concluded that various luminescence quenching processes occur in addition to those caused by the OH vibrations of the coordinating water molecules.

A comparison of the luminescence parameter ($R_{E/M}$ -value and luminescence lifetime of the long-lived component) of Eu(III) associated on *D. hippei* DSM 8344^T cells with the literature revealed similarities to Eu(III) bound to *Shewanella putrefaciens* cells (Ozaki et al., 2004). Most likely carboxyl moieties of the *D. hippei* DSM 8344^T cell envelope are involved in Eu(III) coordination. Furthermore, species 3 showed a high agreement with spectra of a Eu(III) phosphate compound that could be

found during the interaction of the lanthanide with fungal cells (Günther et al., 2022), which is also consistent with the TEM-based analysis of ultrathin sections of the Eu(III)-incubated cells of *D. hippei* DSM 8344^T. A co-localization of Eu(III) with the elements phosphorus and oxygen could be observed on the cell wall, indicating a possible bioprecipitation of Eu(III) with phosphates released by the cell (see Fig. 3). The long lifetime (314 μs) of species 3 indicates a Eu(III) complex with a significantly reduced number of water molecules in its first coordination sphere as would be the case for the phosphate precipitates. Different studies showed that various microorganisms are able to excrete phosphates for heavy metal binding to reduce their toxic effects on the cells (Brock and Schulz-Vogt, 2011; Comeau et al., 1986; Merroun et al., 2011; Reitz et al., 2014; Schulz and Schulz, 2005; Zhu et al., 2023). Studies with the bacterium *Bacillus thuringiensis* X-27 showed the occurrence of uranium precipitates with cellular released phosphates after only 0.5 h of incubation (Zhu et al., 2023). This may also explain the fast onset of the formation of the phosphate species in the TRLFS studies.

A reduction of Eu(III) to Eu(II) by the cells could not be observed by luminescence spectroscopy (data not shown), which was tested with parameters similar to those used to characterize various aqueous Eu(II) complexes known from the literature (Basal et al., 2020; Kuda-Wedagedara et al., 2015; Zhan et al., 2020). Furthermore, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy, which was applied to some of the samples, showed no evidence of an ongoing bioreduction of the lanthanide (data not shown), as was the case for *Clostridium* sp. 2611 (Maleke et al., 2019). The redox potentials of the $\text{SO}_4^{2-}/\text{HSO}_3^-$ and $\text{Eu}^{3+}/\text{Eu}^{2+}$ redox pairs are -0.516 V and -0.903 V , respectively (Ekanger et al., 2016), which means that sulfate reduction per se cannot shift the redox potential enough to cause a reduction of europium. The fact that *Clostridium* sp is able to reduce the lanthanide may be due to a special metabolism of the strain used.

The species distribution in Fig. 5b showed that it was unfortunately not possible to break down the first phase of the bioassociation experiment more precisely. Within the first 20 min, the initial binding of Eu(III) to the cells took place. After that, the proportions of the three extracted species hardly changed. This means that the biosorption of Eu(III) on the cells was completed after a very short period of time. In contrast, after 24 h, changes in the species distribution occurred. Species 1 and 3 were decreasing, whereas the proportion of species 2 increased. It is possible that remodeling of the Eu(III) binding motifs took place through cellular processes. However, further studies, such as proteome analyses, would be needed to obtain more detailed information about the processes involved.

Fig. 5. a) Spectra extracted via PARAFAC (Drobot et al., 2015) from the time-resolved emission spectra of the resuspended cell pellets with an initial Eu(III) concentration of 110 μM (species 1: $R_{E/M} = 0.52$; species 2: $R_{E/M} = 3.10$; species 3: $R_{E/M} = 1.35$). b) Corresponding spectroscopic distribution of the Eu(III) species.

3.5. Eu(III) mapping via fluorescence spectroscopy

In addition, the speciation of Eu(III) in the cell aggregates of *D. hippei* DSM 8344^T was investigated by chemical microscopy. This method provides spatially resolved distribution maps of the Eu(III) species. Since the measuring time for an investigation is several hours, a sample was examined after 24 h of incubation with 110 μM Eu(III). In this sample two Eu(III) species could be localized in the cell aggregates (Fig. 6).

The luminescence emission spectra of the two Eu(III) species deconvoluted with NIFA (Fig. 6b) can be distinguished on the basis of the $R_{E/M}$ value and the characteristic 7F_4 transition. Both species 1 and 2 agree very well in terms of their $R_{E/M}$ values with the extracted species 2 and 3 from the fluorescence spectroscopic investigations of the cell pellets. It can be concluded that they are the same species in both experiments. Species 1 (green), with its spectral shape, a weak 7F_0 transition, and a very high $R_{E/M}$ value of 4.50, depicted spectral similarities to Eu(III), which is bound to carboxyl groups of *Shewanella putrefaciens* cells, for example. Species 2 (violet), on the other hand, showed spectral similarities with Eu(III) bound to inorganic phosphates (Günther et al., 2022; Stadler et al., 2022). Species 2 could therefore correspond to the above described accumulations of Eu(III) that were also visible in the TEM images. Species 1 is characterized by locally very high luminescence intensities (up to a value of over 30), whereas species 2 showed its maximum at a value of about 4.5. However, both species revealed a similar distribution over the total area of the cell aggregate.

In contrast to the time-dependent fluorescence spectroscopy studies of the cell pellets, the spatially resolved study of Eu(III) speciation did not reveal any loosely bound Eu(III) complexes. This may be due to the concentration differences between the solution and the cell agglomerate resulting from the association of Eu(III) with the cells. Despite the fact that only a small proportion of the Eu(III) interacts with the cells, there was an enrichment of Eu(III) on the cell surface and thus an increased

luminescence intensity.

4. Conclusions

Studies on the interaction of microorganisms with trivalent lanthanides such as Eu(III) play an important role in radioecological investigations due to their similar chemical behavior compared to trivalent actinides such as Am(III) or Cm(III). Overall, measurements of the Eu(III) concentrations in the supernatant revealed that only a small fraction of the lanthanide interacted with *D. hippei* DSM 8344^T cells under the applied conditions. A possible explanation could be a shielding of the Eu(III) ions by a strong complexation with lactate ligands in the supernatants as determined by luminescence spectroscopy. Fluorescence microscopy showed a partial aggregation of the cells and a partial cell death with increasing incubation times and Eu(III) concentrations. In addition, TEM imaging coupled with EDXS-based analysis revealed the formation of phosphate-containing Eu(III) aggregates on the cell surface indicating that the occurring interaction mechanisms cannot be explained just by a simple biosorption of Eu(III) by the cells. The formation of a phosphate species already after very short incubation times was verified by TRLFS studies of the cell pellets. Moreover, they also showed the presence of a second cell-bound Eu(III) species. Complementary chemical microscopy of Eu(III)-incubated cell aggregates confirmed the TRLFS results and showed a local distribution of the different Eu(III) complexes. However, no reduction of Eu(III) to Eu(II) could be detected by either luminescence spectroscopy or X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy. In conclusion, this study provides new insights into the interaction mechanisms of a sulfate-reducing bacterium with trivalent lanthanides and actinides and helps to close existing gaps in a comprehensive safeguard concept for a final repository for high-level radioactive waste.

Fig. 6. a) Visible-light microscopy image of an agglomerate of *D. hippei* DSM 8344^T cells after 24 h incubation with 110 μM Eu(III) (artificial Opalinus Clay pore water, pH 5.5, 10 mM sodium lactate) with superimposed Eu(III) species distribution within the ROI, b) deconvoluted Eu(III) luminescence emission spectra (species 1: $R_{E/M} = 4.50$; species 2: $R_{E/M} = 1.30$), c) and d) local distribution of the two Eu(III) species within the ROI ($\lambda_{\text{exc.}} = 532$ nm, exposure time: 10 s, ROI: 50×50 μm , step size: 1 μm).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Stephan Hilpmann: Investigation, Methodology, Data curation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing – original draft, **Henry Moll:** Investigation, Methodology, Data curation, Formal analysis, Validation, Writing – original draft, **Björn Drobot:** Investigation, Methodology, Data curation, Formal analysis, Validation **Manja Vogel:** Investigation, Methodology, Data curation, Formal analysis, Validation, Writing – review & editing, **René Hübner:** Investigation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing, **Thorsten Stumpf:** Supervision, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Resources, **Andrea Cherkouk:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Validation, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgments

The authors gratefully acknowledge the funding provided by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) (Grant 02NUK053E) and the Helmholtz Association (Grant SO-093), as well as a partial funding by the Helmholtz Association, grant PIE-0007 (CROSSING). Furthermore, funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Grant Agreement No. 95237 (SurfBio) is acknowledged. We also thank Sabrina Beutner and Stefanie Bachmann for multiple ICP-MS measurements, Michael Puhlmann for his support in the laboratory, and Dr. Dieter Schild from the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology for X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy measurements. In addition, we would like to thank Dr. Thomas Kurth and Susanne Kretzschmar from the Center for Regenerative Therapies Dresden (CRTD) for the preparation of the TEM specimens. Additionally, the use of the HZDR Ion Beam Center TEM facilities and the funding of TEM Talos by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF; grant No. 03SF0451) in the framework of HEMCP are acknowledged.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.ecoenv.2023.115474](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2023.115474).

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